

To cite this article:

Malaei Zarandi, A., Mokhtari Dinani, M., & Nazarian Madavani, A. (2016). Relationship between Quality of Work Life and Perceived Organizational Performance in Youth and Sports Ministry's Staff. *Journal of Human Resource Management in Sport*, 3(2), 205-219

2016 / Vol. 3 / No. 2 / Pages 205-219

Shahrood University of Technology

Journal of Human Resource Management in Sport

Relationship between Quality of Work Life and Perceived Organizational Performance in Youth and Sports Ministry's Staff

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Received: 10 March 2016 Accepted: 28 August 2016

DOI :[10.22044/shm.2016.837](https://doi.org/10.22044/shm.2016.837)

Abstract

Objective: The aim of this study was to determine the relationship between the quality of work life and the perceived organizational performance in the Youth and Sports Ministry's staff.

Methodology: The population sample was all the employees of the Ministry of Youth and Sports (N=430). Based on the Morgan table, 200 people were selected as the sample. The Hersey and Goldsmith (2013) organizational performance standard questionnaire and the Walton (1973) quality of work life questionnaire were used to collect the data. Data analysis was descriptive (mean, standard deviation, frequency, percentage, inferential statistics Shapiro-Wilk test, Pearson correlation, one-sample T-Test, and multiple regression).

Results: The results obtained showed that there were significant relationships between the components of the quality of work life and the organizational performance. Also the regression analysis showed that the quality of work life predicted the perceived organizational performance. In addition, development of human capabilities ($\beta = 0.411$), social integration ($\beta = 0.175$), providing opportunities for growth and continuous security ($\beta = 0.172$), and fair and enough payment ($\beta = 0.139$) have the most significant abilities to predict the perceived organizational performance for the Youth and Sports Ministry's staff.

Conclusion: The Youth and Sports Ministry administrators need to enhance the quality of work life for their employees as a determinant of the organizational performance.

Keywords: Quality of working life, Organizational performance, Ministry of Sports and Youth.

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